

Reaction of some rices to root-knot nematode

B. Swain, J.S. Prasad, and Y.S. Rao,
Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack
753006, India

We screened 26 rices for resistance to root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola* Golden and Birchfield 1968. Polypots (150 g capacity) were filled with steam sterilized soil (3 loam: 1 sand) and 10 seeds of each rice variety were sown, 1/pot in 3 sets. When seedlings were 5 d old, 200 infective *M. graminicola* juveniles were inoculated in each pot. Thirty-five days after inoculation, the seedlings were uprooted, washed, fixed in 4% formalin, stained in lactophenol cotton-blue, and the number of egg masses per plant was recorded. Varieties with less than one egg mass were classified as resistant and the others as susceptible.

MW-10, Daya, CR190-103, and IR36 were highly resistant (see table). Although earlier reports indicated that Ramsa and TKM6 were resistant, our test at a high inoculum level showed they were susceptible. ☞

Reaction of rice varieties to root-knot nematode, Cuttack, India.

Variety	Mean number of egg masses ^a
MW10	0.6 a
Daya	0.9 ab
IR36	0.9 ab
CR190-103	1.0 ab
Pratap	1.4 abc
Lalnakanda-41	1.5 bcd
IR50	1.7 bcde
Kesari	1.8 cde
TKM 6	1.8 cde
Ratna	1.8 cde
Jajati	1.9 cde
TKM 9	1.9 cdef
Hamsa	2.2 cdef
Rajeswari	2.2 cdef
Kumar	2.3 defg
Rudra	2.4 efg
Jaya	2.4 efg
Sankar	2.4 efg
Sathi	2.4 efg
Akashi	2.4 efg
Suphala	2.7 fgh
OR164-7-1	2.7 fghi
Hema	3.1 ghij
IR8	3.5 hij
Annapurna	3.6 ij
Parijat	4.0 j

^a Average of 3 replications. Separation of means by DMRT at the 1% level.

Soil and Crop Management

Efficacy of slow-release N fertilizers on rice in coastal soils of Karnataka

A.M. Krishnappa, K. Kenchaiah, B.N. Patil, B.K. Balakrishna Rao, and N.A. Janardhana Gowda, Agricultural Research Station, Kankanady, Mangalore 575002, Karnataka, India

In 1984 wet season, we evaluated prilled urea (PU), lac-coated urea (LCU), neem cake-blended urea (NCU), urea supergranules (USG), and sulfur-coated urea (SCU) at 38, 75, 113, and 150 kg N/ha for rice in midland soils of coastal Karnataka. Soil was a fine, loamy, mixed isohyperthermic Ustoxtropept with pH 5.2, 0.99% organic C, 292 kg available P/ha, and 92 kg available K/ha. The experiment was in split-plot design, with N as main plots and sources as subplots. A no-N control was included.

Three 29-d-old IET3232 (medium duration) seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing on 20 Jan. All plots received 75-88 kg PK/ha at planting. One-half PU was applied at planting and 25% at tillering and at panicle initiation. LCU, NCU, and SCU were applied at transplanting, and USG was applied 8-10 cm deep between 4 hills in alternate rows, 7 d after transplanting. The field was flooded from transplanting to maturity. The crop was protected from insects, diseases, and weeds, and was harvested 6 Nov.

Fertilizer levels, sources, and interactions gave significantly different yields (see table). Yield increased with N level. Slow-release fertilizers performed

Yield response of rice to unburned and burned rice husk

A.A. Jakhro, Institute of Agriculture, Timbang Menggaris, Kota Belud, Sabah, Malaysia

We studied the effect of unburned and burned rice husk on rice yield in a pot

Influence of N levels and sources on rice yield, Mangalore, India.

N form	Grain wt/hill (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>No N (control)</i>		
None	12.1	4.0
<i>38 kg N/ha</i>		
PU	13.0	4.3
LCU	13.0	4.3
NCU	14.1	4.7
USG	14.7	4.9
SCU	15.1	5.0
<i>75 kg N/ha</i>		
PU	13.9	4.6
LCU	13.9	4.8
NCU	14.2	4.9
USG	14.2	4.9
SCU	15.8	5.3
<i>113 kg N/ha</i>		
PU	13.7	4.7
LCU	15.1	5.0
NCU	14.4	5.0
USG	15.2	5.1
SCU	17.7	5.9
<i>150 kg N/ha</i>		
PU	14.9	4.9
LCU	15.1	5.0
NCU	15.5	5.2
USG	13.3	4.4
SCU	15.4	5.1
CD (0.05)		
Levels	ns	0.3
Sources	1.2	0.2
Sources at fixed level of N	ns	0.5
Levels at different source	ns	0.5

better than PU at all N levels, with SCU giving highest yields. Yield with SCU or USG at 38 or 75 kg N/ha was similar to yield with PU at 113 or 150 kg N/ha. At 150 kg N/ha, yields with SCU and USG declined. N level did not significantly affect tiller number or grain weight per hill, but sources did. ☞

experiment. Soil was a clay loam with pH 5.6, 1.2% organic matter, 10 ppm Bray P, 2.8 meq available K/100 g soil, and 0.08% N. Treatments of no rice husk (control) and unburned or burned rice husk at 10 t/ha were assigned in a randomized complete block design with 6 replications. Four IR42 seedlings were transplanted in each pot. Water level